

**SOCIAL SUPPORT AND RELIGIOSITY AS PREDICTORS OF
DEPRESSION AMONG STUDENTS IN DELTA STATE
UNIVERSITY, ABRAKA**

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the influence of social support and religiosity in predicting depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka. Three hypotheses derived from the specific objectives of the study were tested. This study is cross sectional in nature and adopts the survey design. The study used quantitative data and this was gathered with questionnaire. The questionnaire was used to elicit response from 300 respondents that constitute the sample size. Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Simple Regression Analysis was used to test the hypotheses. After careful analysis of data, it was discovered that social support is a significant predictor of depression ($r = -0.35$, $\beta = -0.15$, $p < 0.05$), with increased social support associated with decreased depression while religiosity does not have a significant influence on depression ($r = -0.01$, $\beta = -0.00$). The model explained approximately 12% of the variance in depression scores (adjusted $r^2 = 0.12$). As regards the research findings, the following were recommended; interventions aimed at reducing depression should focus on developing and strengthening social connections, a multi-faceted approach is recommended for the enhancement of social support networks for individuals struggling with depression, policymakers should prioritize funding for programs that enhance social support networks for individuals struggling with depression, mental health professionals should assess social support networks as part of depression diagnosis and consider religiosity as a secondary factor in addressing depression, adopting a comprehensive approach that addresses the complex relationships between religiosity, social support, and depression.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

In recent years, the mental health of students has become a significant concern within educational institutions and the broader society. The transition to higher education, accompanied by academic pressures, social adjustments, and increased independence, can pose challenges to students' well-being. Among the various mental health concerns, depression stands out as a prevalent and impactful condition that affects students' academic performance, personal relationships, and overall quality of life. As educators and mental health professionals strive to address this issue, there is a growing interest in understanding the factors that influence depression among students, particularly in the higher institution and how it can be managed.

Depression is a debilitating and pernicious cluster of symptoms that may persist for a period of days, weeks, months, or even years. It is an affective disorder that roots from a combination of psychological, biological and environmental factors, which presents with depressed mood, loss of interest or pleasure, decreased energy, feelings of guilt or low self-worth, disturbed sleep or appetite, and poor concentration (Watson, et al, 2022; Dabana & Gobir, 2018). Scientifically, in addition to bad mood, depression is a disorder that also displays signs of anxiety, negative and infrequent suicidal thoughts, panic, increased

appetite or weight loss, sleep disorders, reduction in the enjoyment of fun activities, and energy loss (DSM-IV, 1994). Kiringlen et. al (2001) said depression is one of the most common mental illnesses amongst youths in Western society. An estimated one in six people, or nearly seventeen percent of American citizens, will experience depression at a point in time during their lifetime, according to the American Psychiatric Association. So, about seven percent of American citizens encounters at least one major depressive episode a year. Though symptoms of depression can start at any age, but it is most likely to start during an individual's teenage years or in his or her 20s (Watson, et al. 2022). A large amount of research that has also examined depression and its numerous forms in different Western societies shows that about fifteen percent of adults (twenty-five percent among women and twelve percent among men) experienced depression at least once in their lifetime (Kaplan, 1994). While other studies (Steffens et al, 2000) discovered a higher percentage (between nine and twenty), stating that a large amount of those individuals did not access standard treatment.

Debra Fulghum Bruce in her article which was later reviewed by Smitha Bhandari (2023), stated the different types of depression and these includes: 1) major depressive disorder, which makes one feel depressed most of the time for 2 weeks or longer; 2) persistent depressive disorder, this term is used to describe two conditions previously known as dysthymia and depression here lasts for 2 years or longer; 3) bipolar disorder, which is also sometimes called "manic depression," has mood episodes that range from

extremes of high energy with an "up" mood to low "depressive" periods (National Institute of Mental Health, 2016); 4) Seasonal affective disorder, this often happens during the winter months, when the days grow short and you get less and less sunlight and it typically goes away in the spring and summer (Cleveland Clinic, 2022); 5) psychotic depression, people with this type of depression have the symptoms of major depression along with "psychotic" symptoms, such as hallucinations, delusions, paranoia; 6) postpartum depression, often happens to women in weeks and months after childbirth (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2013); 7) premenstrual dysphoric disorder, also affect women at the start of their period (University of Michigan Depression Center, 2023); 8) situational depression, which often occurs when one is having trouble managing a stressful event such as a death in the family, a divorce, or losing one's job; 9) atypical depression, is considered to be a "specifier" that describes a pattern of depressive symptoms, which a positive event can temporarily improve your mood.

Psychology Magazine (2023) published an article saying that there are tons of students around the globe who goes through extreme level of stress because of academic pressure on a day-to-day basis. And this pressure is constantly getting worse overtime, as the society places academic excellence on a very high base. Thus, applying a little pressure on students is good for them to getting good grades, but when the pressure becomes extreme, this could lead to deterioration no their physical and mental well-being as there would be an increase in stress pattern. These stress patterns are not just from the parents

and family members alone, but also, the educational institutes and society in general plays a major role in the pressure undergone by students across the globe today. Some of these stress pattern includes examination tension, substance abuse, financial constraints, individuals with physical or mental illness and so on, and this could sometimes cause a dysfunction in their normal day-to-day activity or lead students to think of suicide as the next available option (TED, 2023; ACHA, 2022). Currently, there is a huge increase in competition for employment, which is caused by an increase in world's population, making employment opportunities scarce and rigid. In the world today, despite the fact that there is a surplus number of new fields of study for students to choose from, it only adds to, rather than solve the burden of pressure faced by the students. And this is because, despite the fact that there is an increase in the types of available workforce, there is still a large amount of unemployed educated individuals. There have been multiple stories we come across on a daily basis, wherein highly educated individuals end up either on the streets, jobless, or on a very low-paying job, of which eventually add more pressure on students (Gbenga, O. 2023).

This study delves into the intriguing interplay between social support, religiosity, and depression among students. By investigating the potential impact of these factors, we aim to contribute to a deeper understanding of the mechanisms underlying depression management within the student population. Through a comprehensive review of existing literature, analysis of relevant research methodologies, and interpretation of empirical

findings, this study seeks to shed light on the intricate relationship between social support, religiosity, and the effective mitigation of depression symptoms among students.

Two factors that have gained attention in this context are social support and religiosity. Social support refers to the network of interpersonal relationships, including friends, family, and peers, that individuals rely on during times of stress and difficulty. Social support is remarkably significant for preserving high-quality physical and mental health. Generally, it seems that positive social support of a higher quality can increase resilience to stress, aid the defense against evolving trauma-related psychopathology, diminish the functional significances of trauma-induced illnesses, such as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and decrease medical mortality and morbidity (Southwick S. M. et al 2005). Waite (2018), describes social support as any resources that flows from and through social relationships with others. These relationships are based on social interactions and this interaction could be real, implied, virtual, imagined, momentary and ongoing. From a medical perspective, social support is considered as the accessible assistance for an individual by means of social ties with other people, groups, or the community at general (Ozbay et al., 2008). While religiosity, on the other hand, encompasses the degree of religious belief, participation, and practices in an individual's life. More than eighty percent of the world's populace is associated with a religion group (Pew-Templeton Global Religious Future Project 2020). Altogether, almost twenty percent points out that they are not religiously connected to any group. The percentage of persons

who are not religious affiliated is rising in many countries today, and this rise is mostly influenced by adolescents and emerging adults (Pew Research Center 2018; Bullard 2016; Fetterolf and Poushter 2019). Being religious and not being religious may seem like two different categories. On the other hand, study that delves into the practices and beliefs of cultural groups and their members individually finds out that boundaries are porous between secularism, religiosity, and spirituality. Both social support and religiosity have been associated with better mental health outcomes, but their roles as predictors of depression among students remain complex and multifaceted.

In the subsequent chapters, we will explore the theoretical frameworks that underpin the connections between social support, religiosity, and depression. Additionally, we will outline the research methodology employed to investigate these relationships, providing insights into the data collection and analysis procedures. The results of our study will be presented and discussed in light of existing literature, followed by implications for educational institutions and mental health practitioners. Ultimately, this research work aspires to contribute to the ongoing discourse on student mental health by unraveling the potential significance of social support and religiosity as predictors of depression.

1.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Depression is the condition that has regrettably been on the increase in the sub-Saharan part of Africa precisely the West African sub region. The negative implication of

depression has taken its toll on the nation (Nigeria), this may be as a result of present harsh economic condition which has led to the death of several people most especially the Nigerian youths who happen to be the leaders of tomorrow (UNICEF, 2021; Edet, N.E. 2023). The constant lack of social support to ensure their growth and development which precipitates to low self-esteem has led the youths to usage of different drugs and involvement in diverse criminal activities in other to survive which in most cases are not self-sustaining, this leads to depression (Gbenga, O. 2023). Hence, this study intends to find out how social support and religiosity can serve as a predictor of depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The major aim of the study is to examine the impact of social support and religiosity as predictors to depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka.

- i. To examine the rate of depression occurrences among students in Delta State University, Abraka.
- ii. To examine the impact of social support on depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka.
- iii. To assess the impact of religiosity on depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka.

- iv. To examine the factors that reduces the incidences among students in Delta State University, Abraka.
- v. To recommend ways of reducing reoccurrences of depression in students.

1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study covers social support and religiosity as predictors to depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka. In terms of variables scope, the study will cover two independent variables namely: social support and religiosity and one dependent variable that is depression. Under social support, the study will cover parental support, peer support, community support, neighbor support and counselor's support. While under religiosity the study will cover cognition, feelings and behavior.

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study holds several important implications for both academia and practical applications within educational institutions and mental health settings. This study's significance lies in its potential to inform educational policies, improve mental health services, and foster a better understanding of the multifaceted factors influencing depression among students. By shedding light on the roles of social support and religiosity, this research contributes to the broader efforts aimed at promoting students' mental well-being and overall success. The exploration of the relationship between social support,

religiosity, and depression among students offers valuable contributions in the following ways:

1. **Enhanced Understanding of Coping Mechanisms:** By investigating how social support and religiosity influence depression, this study provides insights into the adaptive strategies that students employ to manage their mental well-being. Understanding these coping mechanisms can inform the development of targeted interventions and support programs.
2. **Informed Mental Health Services:** Educational institutions often struggle to provide effective mental health services to their students. The findings of this study can guide universities and colleges in tailoring their support services to better address the specific needs of students, taking into account the role of social support and religiosity in depression management.
3. **Holistic Approaches to Student Well-being:** Recognizing the potential contributions of social support and religiosity to depression emphasizes the importance of a holistic approach to student well-being. This encourages institutions to consider not only academic success but also emotional and psychological welfare as integral components of the student experience.
4. **Guidance for Peer and Family Involvement:** The study's findings may underscore the importance of involving peers and family members in supporting students with depression. It can offer guidance on how friends, family, and religious

communities can play a role in providing a supportive environment conducive to effective depression management.

5. **Contribution to Academic Discourse:** This study contributes to the existing body of literature on student mental health by addressing a specific aspect of depression. The insights gained from this research can serve as a foundation for future studies exploring the complex interplay between psychological, social, and religious factors.
6. **Promotion of Cultural Sensitivity:** The role of religiosity in depression highlights the cultural diversity among student populations. This study encourages a more culturally sensitive approach to mental health care, recognizing the significance of religious beliefs and practices in influencing coping mechanisms.

1.5 OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF TERMS

Depression: This is characterized by persistent feelings of sadness, loss of interest, and a range of emotional and physical problems that impair daily functioning.

Religiosity: This is referred to as the degree of religious beliefs, practices, and involvement an individual engages in.

Social Support: This refers to the perceived comfort, care, assistance, and information that an individual receives from others, including family, friends, and significant others.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 MENTAL HEATH

World Health Organization (2017) defined depression as a pathological state that is associated with feelings of loss or guilt and characterized by sadness, lowering of self-esteem, disturbed sleep or appetite, feelings of tiredness, and poor concentration. It is a mood disorder characterized by low mood, a feeling of sadness, and a general loss of interest in things. Depression causes feelings of sadness and/or a loss of interest in activities once enjoyed by an individual (Cohen B. D. 2008). Clinical depression can be diagnosed by duration and severity of sadness. Normal sadness or short-lived feelings of depression which do not result in impaired functioning are not clinical depression. Clinical depression is diagnosed when the signs of depression are present in an individual for at least a period of 2 weeks. Clinically depressed people do not take part in social, occupational, and over all daily functioning activities. Some of the symptoms of clinical depression include frequent depressed mood, nearly every day changes in appetite that result in weight losses unrelated to dietary, loss of energy or increased fatigue, increased alcohol or drug use, thought of suicide etc. It is characterized by feelings of sadness, loneliness, despair, low self-esteem and self-reproach, accompanying signs include psychomotor retardation or less frequent agitation, withdrawal from social contact and vegetative states such as loss of

appetite and insomnia. Depression among youth and adolescents is a common phenomenon in Nigeria (Uwaoma, 2016). In contrast to the normal state of sadness, severe depression, which could be also called Major Depressive Disorder (MDD), can drastically impair an individual's ability to function in social situations. People with Major Depressive Disorder often have feelings of hopelessness, worthlessness and despair, as well as suicidal thoughts (Cohen B. D. 2008). According to the World Health Organization in 2018, Major Depressive Disorder was ranked third in the world in terms of disease problem, and it was predicted that by year 2030, it would rank number one on the chart (Malhi, G. S. et al. 2018). There are many cases of depressive symptoms that are overwhelming the youths now. An extreme depressive disorder can have serious consequences on an individual such as abuse of drug substance and addiction, social withdrawal and isolation, suicidal thoughts and actions, decline in academic performance and risk of dropping out (TED, 2023).

Factors recognized by Karl Peltzer et al (2013) responsible for the increase in risk of depression among students in African universities have been identified as follows: 1) socio-demographic factors such as higher year of study or older age (Ibrahim et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2013), lower socio-economic status (Steptoe et al., 2007; Ibrahim et al., 2012; Chen et al., 2013; Ibrahim et al., 2013), female gender (Adewuya et al., 2006); 2) anxiety and traumatic life events including life stressors (Reyes-Rodríguez et al., 2013; Adewuya et al., 2006), post-traumatic stress disorder (Peltzer, 1998), witnessing parental violence (Nicodimos et al., 2009), and gender-based violence (Gelaye et al., 2009); 3) other health

risk behavior such as obesity or overweight (Zhao et al., 2009; Wilson et al., 2012), physical immobility (Taliaferro et al., 2009), sleeping difficulties (Angelone et al., 2011), treatable unintended injury (Chen et al., 2005), HIV risk behavior (Agardh et al., 2012; Lundberg et al., 2011), and skin lightening product usage (Ladizinski et al., 2011); 4) social variables including religiosity and/or spirituality (Berry & York, 2011), social support (Kim, 2001), low sense of control (Steptoe et al., 2007); and 5) poor academic performance (Yusoff, 2013).

One important variable in dealing with depression and how it can be controlled is social support. Social support is often referred to the various forms of assistance and comfort that individuals receive from their social networks which can include family, friends, colleagues and community members. Social support happens when there is a presence of social network (Langford C. P, et al. 1997; Kent et al. 2018); this model is mostly used in a broader sense in referring to any procedure through which health and well-being is being provided by social relationships (Cohen S, et al. 2000; Kent et al. 2018). Social support by our social network proves to be important for our overall wellbeing and the lack of a good social support network may lead to loneliness, as relationships with family, friends, and members in organizations contribute to social integration (Kent et al. 2018; Taylor S. E. 2011). Social support and social networks as described by Kent de Grey R, et al (2018), are in different segment; mainly these can be seen as (1) functionally and

structurally and (2) formally and informally, for instance, caregiving can be a formal support to individuals who do not have close friends.

Another significant variable in this study is Religiosity. Religiosity is strong religious belief. It is the quality of being very or too religious. According to Hills (2014), religiosity typically refers not only to a belief in a higher entity or something greater than oneself but also formal involvement in organized religious activities and specific, measurable acts such as prayer, meditation, service attendance, religious readings, and affiliation with a particular religion or place of worship. A key characteristic of religion is that it is organized in a hierarchical fashion with an identified authority figure such as a priest, pastor, or rabbi presiding (Hills, 2014). Koenig (2008) identified three general types of religiosity: organizational, nonorganizational, and intrinsic. Organizational religiosity typically involves public or group activities and is most commonly measured by one's religious service attendance. Non organizational religiosity, by contrast, is more private and typically occurs on a person's own time, alone, encompassing activities such as reading religious texts, praying, and/or meditating. Intrinsic religiosity measures the degree of an individual religious motivation or commitment. The relationship between mental health and various psychosocial factors has been a subject of considerable interest within both research and clinical contexts. Among these factors, social support and religiosity have emerged as significant predictors of mental health outcomes, particularly in the realm of depression among student populations.

2.2 SOCIAL SUPPORT AND DEPRESSION

Social support refers to the various ways in which individuals aid others to overcome circumstances of life. It has been documented as playing an important and positive role in the health and well-being of individuals. Social support and relationships have been shown to be one of the protective factors against the occurrence of mental disorders (Cobb, 1976) and in the treatment of psychological disorders (Bryant, 2010). However, social support has often been summarized as a network of individuals on whom one can rely for psychological or material support to cope effectively with stress. According to Towey, (2018) social support is theorized to be offered in the form of instrumental support (i.e., material aid), appraisal/informational support (i.e., advice, guidance, feedback), or emotional support (i.e., reassurance of worth, empathy, affection). Friends respond with empathy, concern, and advice to a person facing difficulties or loss. They tend to boost self-esteem and confidence by offering compliments and reassurance (Price H. R. 2009). Social support enhances quality of life and provides a buffer against adverse life events like depression (Towey, 2018). More so, according to Cohen, (2016) Social support also has important effects on one's health and well-being. Overall, social support has been linked with good health and well-being as well as improved adjustment to specific chronic illnesses, such as cardiovascular disorders (Gluckman P. D. 2007; Weinman J. A. 1997), cancer (Cecilia Kuepper 2024), HIV/AIDS (Deshira D. Wallace, et al. 2019) and psoriasis (Konrad J. et al. 2012).

A growing body of research indicates that strong social support systems are associated with lower levels of depression and better mental health outcomes among students. When students perceive that they have access to empathetic friends, family members, or mentors, they are more likely to experience reduced depressive symptoms. Supportive relationships provide a buffer against the stressors inherent in the academic environment, allowing students to develop effective coping strategies.

Additionally, studies have shown that different sources of social support, such as peer support, family support, and academic support, can contribute differently to depression. Peer support, for instance, may facilitate a sense of belonging and connectedness (Schwartz-Mette RA, 2020), while family support may provide a stable foundation for emotional well-being (Yunmiao Yu. 2015). Therefore, the nature and quality of social connections can influence how effectively students manage depression symptoms.

2.3 RELIGIOSITY AND DEPRESSION

Religiosity, encompassing religious beliefs, practices, and involvement, has also been linked to mental health outcomes. Religious engagement offers a structured framework for meaning-making and purpose, providing individuals with a sense of guidance and support during challenging times. The World Health Organization (2017) projects that, by the year 2020, major depression will be the world's second most debilitating condition; only cardiovascular disease will cause more disability among

persons aged 15 to 44 in the USA. Religious involvement is also common today, with surveys showing that a significant proportion of the world's population has religious beliefs and practices that are important to daily life (Bonelli, 2012). In another survey by Dew (2012) with representative populations of 143 countries (n = 140,000), found that 92 percent of people in 32 developing countries indicated religion was an important part of daily life and influences response to issues of life. Likewise, a survey of developed countries by Angus (2017) involving 5,800 adults in Australia, Britain, Canada, China, Egypt, France, Germany, India, Israel, Italy, Japan, Lebanon, Mexico, Russia, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Republic of Korea, Spain, Turkey, and the United States found that 48% of respondents said religion is a very important component of their daily lives and admit that religious or spiritual beliefs and practices may be used to cope with or adapt to stressful life circumstances. For students who identify as religious, religiosity can serve as a source of comfort and solace, helping them cope with stressors and depressive symptoms. Studies examining the relationship between religiosity and depression among students have yielded mixed findings. While some research suggests that higher levels of religiosity are associated with better mental health outcomes, others indicate that the relationship may be more complex, influenced by factors such as religious doubts or conflicts. Furthermore, the degree of religiosity and the type of religious practices undertaken may play a role in how effectively religiosity serves as a predictor of depression. Research undertaken around the world on Muslim populations has indicated a clear and positive correlations between

religiosity and a strong sense of happiness, with less mentally-induced symptoms, more optimism and less anxiety and with physical well-being and enthusiasm (Qutaiba Agbaria 2013; Abdel-Khalek, 2002, 2005).

2.4 INTERACTION BETWEEN SOCIAL SUPPORT AND RELIGIOSITY

The interplay between social support and religiosity is an area of growing interest. Some studies suggest that individuals who are part of supportive religious communities may experience enhanced social support, leading to better mental health outcomes. On the other hand, tensions between religious beliefs and social networks can also arise, potentially impacting depression (Schwartz-Mette RA, 2020; Stephen Weatherhead, & Anna Daiches 2010; Qutaiba Agbaria, 2013). Exploring the dynamics of this interaction can provide a nuanced understanding of how these factors collectively influence students' ability to manage depressive symptoms.

The connection between depression and social support in youth has been critically researched on through experimental studies. It was discovered that a higher level of family support, friend support, and the entire emotional support has regularly been connected with reduced chances of youth depression (Hall-Lande, et al. 2007; Houlberg, B., et al. 2011; Nasser, E.H. et al. 2005; Schraedley, P.K., et al. 1999). Social connections could increase overall well-being through improving an individual's feelings of stability and predictability, improving an individual's sense of belonging, purpose, and security, enhancing self-esteem through social recognition of self-worth, and preserving positive

emotional states (Cohen, S., et al. 2001). Religiosity on the other hand, is a crucial psychological asset that youth can draw on for improvement of their mental well-being. Religiosity refers to a person's religious affiliation and beliefs and the extent to which they pray and participate in religious activities (Koenig, H.G., et al., 1997). Religious attendance, self-ranked religiousness and positive religious experience have been associated with lower depressive symptoms in adolescents (Sinha, J.W., et al. 2007; Pearce, M.J, et al, 2003; Schapman and Inderbitzen-Nolan, 2002).

In conclusion, the literature on social support and religiosity as predictors of depression among students underscores their significant roles in shaping mental health outcomes. However, the exact nature of these relationships is complex and multifaceted, influenced by individual differences, cultural contexts, and the dynamic interplay between social networks and religious beliefs. The subsequent sections of this research will delve deeper into the theoretical frameworks and research methodologies that contribute to a comprehensive understanding of these connections.

2.5 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework guiding this study draws upon two fundamental perspectives: Social Support Theory and Theoretical Models of Religiosity's Influence on Mental Health. These perspectives are integral in comprehending how the interaction between social support and religiosity can predict depression among students. In inclusion to this research, we would also be looking at other theoretical framework such as the

Cognitive Behavioral Theory and Attachment Theory as they aid this study in ways that reduces the risk of depression and promote overall well-being of students.

2.5.1 SOCIAL SUPPORT THEORY

Social Support Theory posits that individuals who possess robust social networks are better equipped to cope with stressors and, consequently, experience fewer negative psychological outcomes. Cohen and Wills (1985) assert that social support offers a range of assistance, including emotional (i.e., feeling loved and cared for by others), informational (i.e., getting advice, guidance and valuable information from others), and instrumental support (i.e., receiving tangible help, such as financial assistance and practical aid), which collectively serve as a protective buffer against stress and depression. The cornerstone of this framework is the "Stress-Buffering Hypothesis," which suggests that social support moderates the adverse impact of stress on mental health, particularly for individuals who lack adequate internal coping resources (Cohen & Wills, 1985; Thoits, 2011).

Social support can buffer the negative effects of stress on mental and physical health by providing a sense of belonging, reducing feelings of loneliness, and promoting positive emotions (Cohen et al., 2015). It can also enhance coping skills and resilience by providing individuals with the resources and skills needed to manage stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Furthermore, social support can promote social integration and belonging, which are critical for overall well-being (Cohen et al., 2015). Social support can come from

various sources, including family and friends (Cohen & Wills, 1985), social networks and communities (House, 1981), support groups and organizations (Lieberman & Bliwise, 1985), and professional helpers, such as therapists and counselors (Sarason & Sarason, 1985).

2.5.2 THEORETICAL MODELS OF RELIGIOSITY'S INFLUENCE ON MENTAL HEALTH

Religiosity is frequently examined within theoretical frameworks that illuminate its potential impact on mental health outcomes. Religious communities often serve as natural social networks, fostering emotional and tangible support (Ellison & Levin, 1998). Support from religious communities has also been proven to provide additional source of emotional, practical and informational support to individuals (Koenig et al., 2012). Pargament's "Sacred and Spiritual Struggles" model proposes that conflicts stemming from religious beliefs or experiences can lead to negative emotional outcomes, including depression (Pargament, 1997). Conversely, the "Positive Psychology Perspective" posits that religious beliefs afford individuals a sense of purpose and meaning, contributing to overall well-being (Emmons & Paloutzian, 2003).

2.5.3 INTEGRATION OF SOCIAL SUPPORT AND RELIGIOSITY

The integration of social support and religiosity plays a crucial role in promoting mental health and well-being, particularly in the context of stress and adversity (Cohen et al., 2015). Religious communities can provide emotional, instrumental, and informational

support to individuals, enhancing their sense of belonging and collective coping (Koenig et al., 2012). Conversely, religiosity can provide a sense of meaning, purpose, and belonging, which can enhance social support by fostering a sense of community and shared values (Tajfel & Turner, 1986).

Social support can moderate the relationship between religiosity and mental health outcomes, such as depression and anxiety (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). For instance, individuals with high social support may experience fewer negative effects of stress on mental health (Cohen et al., 2015). Furthermore, religiosity can influence social support seeking and utilization, with religious individuals more likely to seek support from religious sources (Koenig et al., 2012).

Collective coping resources, such as prayer, meditation, or shared religious practices, can also enhance social support (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). Shared values and meaning provided by religiosity can foster a sense of community and shared purpose, further enhancing social support (Tajfel & Turner, 1986). By integrating social support and religiosity, individuals can experience a comprehensive support system that addresses both psychological and spiritual needs, leading to enhanced mental health and well-being (Koenig et al., 2012). This integration can provide a buffer against stress and adversity, promoting resilience and coping. The interplay between social support and religiosity highlights the importance of considering both psychological and spiritual factors in promoting mental health and well-being. By acknowledging and leveraging this

integration, individuals and communities can foster a more holistic approach to mental health support.

2.5.4 COGNITIVE BEHAVIORAL THEORY

Cognitive Behavioral Theory (CBT) is a well-established psychological framework that emphasizes the interplay between thoughts, emotions, and behaviors. It is based on the premise that cognitive processes influence emotional responses and behavior patterns. This theory helps in a number of ways like cognitive restructuring which involves identifying and challenging irrational or negative thoughts and replacing them with more balanced and constructive ones (Rebecca J, S. 2020), encouraging individuals to engage in activities that are rewarding and meaningful in order to increasing their positive experiences thereby reducing avoidance behaviors which can help counteract depressive symptoms (Leanne Q & Keith S, D. 2017), and development of effective coping strategies to help manage stress and emotional distress which includes problem-solving skills, relaxation techniques, and mindfulness practices (Grouport, 2023; Silvia P. et al. 2022).

2.5.5 ATTACHMENT THEORY

Attachment theory is a psychological and evolutionary theory regarding the relationships between humans. This theory was originally developed by psychiatrist and psychoanalyst John Bowlby in 1969-88 (Cassidy J, 1999; Abrams D. B, et al. 2013), and was later expanded by psychologist Mary Ainsworth in the 1960s and '70s (Bernard K, 2013). It provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the development of

emotional bonds and their long-term impact on an individuals' mental health. Its focus is between caregivers and children, and how these bonds shapes an individuals' social and emotional development throughout life. Here in the attachment theory, we consider three major aspects and these are: 1) secure attachment, which develops from consistent responsiveness of a caregiver to a child's needs, causing the individual to have a healthy and trusting relationships, and making it able for them to manage stress and emotions; 2) insecure attachment, causing anxious, avoidant, or disorganization, often as a result of inconsistent or neglectful caregiving, and; 3) internal working models, a mental representation of one's self and others, formed based on early attachment experiences which influences expectations and interactions in an individual's future relationships, affecting how they perceive and seek social support and religiosity (Bretherton I, 1992).

2.6 EMPIRICAL REVIEW

A research conducted by Enike, et al (2021) on social support and religiosity as predictors of depression control among youths in Anambra state, stated that there was a 77.2% positive correlation between depression control and social support, since the probability value of the correlation coefficient, which is 0.015, is less than the critical 0.05 at 5% significance level ($r=0.772$; $p<0.05$); while on religiosity, the results indicates that there is 55.2% positive correlation between depression control and Religiosity, which implies that depression control and Religiosity are strongly correlated since the probability value of the correlation coefficient, which is 0.045, is less than the critical 0.05 at 5%

significance level ($r=0.552$; $p<0.05$). This implies that social support and religiosity are both crucial factors and strong predictors of depression control among undergraduate students of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam. Anambra state, Nigeria.

In another study conducted by Angela U. Ekwonye and her group of researchers (2017) in a faith-based school, they discovered there was a negative significant correlation between social support and depression ($r = -0.201$, $p < 0.05$), and religiosity and depression ($r = -0.127$, $p < 0.05$); an indication that social support and a frequent participation in religious activities are good for mental and emotional well-being of adolescents. But in other studies, some parts of religiosity such as private religious practices were not connected with depressive symptoms in adolescents (Pearce, M. J. et al. 2003; Wenger, S. 2011).

In a research study carried out by Dr. Qutaiba Agbaria (2013) on the contribution of religiosity and social support on depression among Arab students in Israel. The number of participants he used for his study consisted of 280 Arab students from teacher training colleges in the Triangle region in central Israel. The findings indicate that all the resources that were examined contribute to reducing the level of depression, in other words, significant negative correlations were found between the level of religiosity (BETA = -0.54 , $p < 0.001$) and social support (BETA = -0.18 , $p < 0.05$) on depression. These findings are

consistent with those of other studies conducted elsewhere in the world on different populations (Christian and Jewish, as well as Muslim).

2.7 HYPOTHESIS

This study postulates the following hypotheses:

1. Social support will have a significant influence on depression.
2. Religiosity will have a significant influence on depression.
3. There will be a joint influence between social support and religiosity on depression.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study employs a cross-sectional design, capturing data from a single point in time to explore relationships among variables. This design facilitates the examination of associations between social support, religiosity, and depression within the context of students' lives.

3.2 Population and Sampling Technique

A diverse sample of undergraduate students (N = 300) from various academic disciplines and levels in Delta State University, Abraka were used in this study, to ensure diversity in demographics and experiences. Efforts were made to select respondents from different ethnic groups, religion and gender to capture a broad range of experiences.

3.3 METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

Survey Questionnaire:

This research used a self-administered questionnaire to collect data. The questionnaire consists of:

1. **Demographic Information:** This includes information such as age, gender, relationship status and religious affiliation.

2. **Social Support Questionnaire:** The Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) is a widely used questionnaire developed in 1988 by Zimet and his research colleagues. It measures an individual's perception of social support and was utilized in this research study to assess participants perceived social support from family, friends, and academic network. The Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) has a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.85 to 0.91 which demonstrated good reliability. This scale consists of 12 items, with 4 items per subscale (family, friends, significant other). Each item is rated on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = "very strongly disagree" to 7 = "very strongly agree"), with higher scores indicating greater perceived social support.
3. **Religiosity Scale:** The Duke University Religion Index (DUREL) was employed to measure participants religious activity and non-organizational religious activity. This scale was developed by the Duke University Center for Spirituality, Theology, and Health in 2010. It measures three dimensions of religiosity which includes organizational religiousness (i.e., involvement in religious activities), non-organizational religiousness (i.e., personal religious practices and beliefs), and intrinsic religious motivation (i.e., the extent to which religion is a part of one's life and influences their daily decision). The overall scale has high test-retest reliability (intra-class correlation = 0.91), high internal consistence (Cronbach's alpha = 0.78–0.91), high convergent validity with other measures of religiosity (r 's = 0.71–0.86).

The DUREL consist of five items, while the items are in two sections based on their dimensions: first section has two items which covers for the organizational and non-organizational religiousness, which were rated on a 6-point Likert scale (1 = “never” to “more than once a week”); the second section which has three items cover for intrinsic religious motivation, rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = “definitely not true” to 5 = “definitely true of me”), with a higher score indicating higher levels of religiosity.

4. **Depression Assessment:** The Patients Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9), a widely recognized and used screening tool in healthcare and research settings. It was used to assess participants depressive symptoms over the past two weeks. This scale consists of 9 items rated on a 4-point Likert scale (0 = “not at all” to 3 = “nearly every day”), with higher scores indicating a more severe symptoms as it is used to evaluate the feelings of sadness, hopelessness and loss of interest in activities. This scale has a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.86 to 0.89 (average: 0.87), which indicates an excellent internal consistency and reliability as it is a widely used scale for measuring depressive symptoms both in clinical and research settings.

Procedure:

The questionnaires were made up of a total of 30 items of which most of the questions are close-ended. This study was conducted using an online survey platform to facilitate data collection. Upon accessing the survey link, participants first complete a brief sociodemographic questionnaire to collect information on age, gender, marital status and religious affiliation. Following this, participants were asked to complete the self-report measures assessing social support, religiosity and depression level.

3.4 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The appropriate statistical method employed for carrying out an accurate quantitative data analysis on this research includes:

1. **Descriptive Analysis:** Results begin with descriptive statistics which summarized participants' demographic characteristics and their responses to the social support questionnaire, religiosity scale, and depression assessment.
2. **Correlation Analysis:** Correlation coefficients was calculated using Pearson's correlation to determine the strength and direction of relationships between social support, religiosity, and depression scores.
3. **Regression Analysis:** Multiple regression analysis was performed to assess the predictive power of social support and religiosity on depression. Control for potential confounding variables like demographic characteristics.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

This chapter embodies the representation and analyses of data, together with hypothesis testing of data necessary for explaining the influence of social support and religiosity as predictors of depression among university students in Delta State University, Abraka. The instrument of data collection had two parts: section A aiming to describe the sociodemographic characteristics of the respondents; and section B measuring the respondents' response on social support and religiosity as predictors of depression. The responses from the research questionnaires were coded and analyze using IBM-SPSS v.25.

Presentation of Data

A survey link was shared through various mediums (i.e. via emails, WhatsApp groups and private messages). When a total number of three hundred participants was achieved, the link was disabled to restrict further responses, making the total number of participants used for this research 300. The 300 responses retrieved were useful and this represented a return rate of 100% of the questionnaires that were distributed.

4.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE SAMPLE

Table 4.1: Gender Distribution of Respondents

Gender	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	121	40.3
Female	179	59.7
Total	300	100

Table 4.1 clearly shows that out of 300 respondents, 121 were male representing 40.3% while the female was 179, representing 59.7%. This implies that female respondents dominate the male in frequency count and percentage.

Table 4.2: Age of Respondents

Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
16 – 20	96	32
21 – 25	111	37
26 – 30	82	27.3
31 – Above	11	3.7
Total	300	100

Table 4.2 shows the age of respondents. It ascertained that out of 300 respondents 96 (32%) are within the age bracket of 16 – 20, 111 (37%) are within the age bracket of 21 – 25, 82

(27.3%) of the respondents are within the age bracket of 26 – 30 while 11 (3.7%) are from 31 years old and above.

Table 4.3: Marital Status of Respondents

Marital Status	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Single	281	93.7
Married	15	5
Separated	4	1.3
Widowed	0	0
Total	300	100

Table 4.3 shows the marital status of respondents who participated in this study. “Single” had the dominant form as 281 (93.7%) respondents out of 300 claimed they are single. Immediately coming in this category are the married who were 15 after and constituted 5% of the total respondents. The separated marital status category had 4 respondents, constituting 1.3% of the sample respondents and none was widowed.

Table 4.4: Religious Affiliation of Respondents

Religious Affiliation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Christian	287	95.7
Muslim	12	4
Traditional	1	0.3
Total	300	100

Table 4.4 shows us respondent religious affiliation. A total number of 287 (95.7%) out of 300 respondents are Christians, 12 (4%) are Muslims while just 1 (0.3%) respondent is identified as a traditionalist.

4.2 TESTING HYPOTHESES

The decision rule to be used in testing the hypotheses is, if critical value (p) > 0.05 for a two tailed test, accept the null hypothesis but if critical value (p) < 0.05 , reject the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1

Social support will have a significant influence on depression.

Table 4.5: Pearson product moment correlation analysis summary of social support and depression.

Variables	N	M	SD	df	r	r²	Sig.
Social Support	300	4.84	1.29				
				298	-.35	.12	.000
Depression	300	.57	.55				

To predict if social support will have a significant influence on depression, the Pearson correlation coefficient from the table above shows that there is a statistically significant negative correlation between social support and depression ($r = -0.35$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that increased social support is associated with decreased depression. Social support accounted for approximately 12% of the variance in depression scores ($r^2 = 0.12$).

Hypothesis 2

Religiosity will have a significant influence on depression.

Table 4.6: Pearson product moment correlation analysis summary of religiosity and depression.

Variables	N	M	SD	df	r	r²	Sig.
Religiosity	300	4.17	.94				
				298	-.10	.01	.084
Depression	300	.57	.55				

To predict if religiosity will have a significant influence on depression, the Pearson correlation coefficient from the table above found a non-significant weak negative correlation between religiosity and depression ($r = -0.10$, $p = 0.084$), indicating that religiosity does not have a statistically significant influence on depression. Religiosity only accounted for approximately 1% of the variance in depression scores ($r^2 = 0.01$).

Hypothesis 3

There will be a joint influence between social support and religiosity on depression.

Table 4.7: Simple regression analysis predicting social support and religiosity from depression.

Model	B	β	Adjusted R^2	F	P	95% CI	
						LL	UL
Religiosity	-.01	-.00	.12	20.54	.000	-.06	.06
Social Support	-.35	-.15				-.19	-.10

Table 4.7 shows a simple regression analysis predicting social support and religiosity from depression. This study found that social support is a significant predictor of depression ($r = -0.35$, $\beta = -0.15$, $p < 0.05$), with increased social support associated with decreased depression. Religiosity did not have a significant influence on depression. The model explained approximately 12% of the variance in depression scores (adjusted $r^2 = 0.12$).

4.3 RESEARCH FINDINGS

The following are the list of research findings in this study:

1. Religiosity has no significant relationship with depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka.

2. Social support is a significant predictor of depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka.
3. The combination of social support and religiosity explains a moderate portion of depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka.
4. The overall model is statistically significant, indicating a significant relationship between the factors and depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka.
5. Social support is inversely related to depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka, as social support increases, depression decreases.
6. Religiosity does not contribute significantly to predicting depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka, in this model.
7. Social support accounts for a notable portion of the variability in the depression scores among students in Delta State University, Abraka.
8. The model explains approximately 12% of the variance in depression scores among students in Delta State University, Abraka.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 DISCUSSION

This study was designed to examine the influence of social support and religiosity as predictors of depression among students in Delta State University, Abraka. The study's findings suggest that religiosity has a negligible impact on depression, which contradicts previous research that suggested a positive correlation between religiosity and mental health. This discrepancy may be attributed to various factors, such as differences in study populations, methodologies, or measures of religiosity. Although, research by Darren E. Sherkat & Mark D. Reed (1992), suggested that religious participation has no significant influence on depression but has significantly increases self-esteem, they also further said that the frequency of contact and confiding with friends and relatives predict both self-esteem and depression. Additionally, the study's results may indicate that religiosity is not a primary factor in mitigating depression, but rather a secondary or indirect factor.

In contrast, social support emerged as a significant predictor of depression, highlighting the importance of social connections in maintaining good mental health (Cohen et al., 2015). This finding aligns with existing literature that emphasizes the role of social support in buffering against stress, anxiety, and depression (Angela U. E. et al., 2017; Qutaiba Agbaria, 2013; Enike, et al., 2021). The study's results suggest that social support

networks should be a primary focus in developing interventions aimed at reducing depression.

The moderate fit of the model (12% of variance explained) suggests that other factors may also play a role in depression, warranting further research. For instance, other psychological, social, or environmental factors (Kraemer et al., 2001) may contribute to depression, and exploring these factors could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the complex relationships between religiosity, social support, and depression among students in the university. Furthermore, the study's findings highlight the need for a nuanced understanding of the relationships between religiosity, social support, and depression among students in the university. Rather than relying on assumptions or generalizations, mental health professionals should consider the unique experiences and circumstances of individuals when developing interventions (Pargament et al., 2000; Kessler et al., 2003). This may involve tailoring interventions to address specific needs, such as enhancing social support networks or exploring religiosity's indirect benefits.

Furthermore, this research has brought to a halt on the study of the role social support and religiosity plays on depression among undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka. With the results derived from this empirical study, we can boldly say that when it comes to students studying within the Delta State University, Abraka environs, religious participation does not help with their depressive symptoms, instead, those who

seek emotional support from their social circle like their course mates, friends and family have a higher and greater chance of overcoming depression.

The study's results also have implications for future research. For example, exploring the mechanisms underlying the relationships between religiosity, social support, and depression could provide valuable insights into the complex interplay between these factors. Additionally, examining the impact of religiosity and social support on other mental health outcomes, such as anxiety or substance use, could further our understanding of these relationships (Koenig et al., 2012). Generally, this study contributes to our understanding of the complex relationships between religiosity, social support, and depression, and highlights the importance of considering multiple factors when developing effective interventions.

5.2 CONCLUSION

This research investigated the relationships between religiosity, social support, and depression, revealing significant findings that contribute to our understanding of these complex relationships. The results indicate that religiosity has a negligible impact on depression, while social support emerges as a critical factor in reducing depression. The study's findings highlight the importance of considering multiple factors when addressing depression and emphasize the need to prioritize social support networks in interventions aimed at reducing depression.

From the study's results, it is suggested that religiosity may not be a primary factor in mitigating depression, but rather a secondary or indirect factor when it comes to the undergraduate students in Delta State University, Abraka. This finding contradicts previous research, highlighting the need for further exploration of the mechanisms underlying these relationships. The study's findings align with existing literature emphasizing the role of social support in maintaining good mental health. The moderate fit of the model suggests that other factors may also play a role in depression, warranting further research to explore these factors.

Furthermore, this study contributes to our understanding of the complex relationships between religiosity, social support, and depression, highlighting the importance of considering multiple factors when developing effective interventions. The findings have important implications for mental health professionals, policymakers, and researchers, emphasizing the need to prioritize social support networks and explore the complex interplay between religiosity, social support, and depression. Additionally, future research should aim to explore the mechanisms underlying these relationships, examine the impact of religiosity and social support on other mental health outcomes, and develop interventions that address the complex needs of individuals struggling with depression. By doing so, we can work towards developing more effective strategies for reducing depression and promoting good mental health.

5.3 RECOMMENDATION

In light of the findings of this study and the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were proffered:

1. To address the complex relationships between religiosity, social support, and depression, a multi-faceted approach is recommended, thereby prioritizing enhancement of social support networks for individuals struggling with depression, while also considering the potential secondary or indirect role of religiosity in addressing depression.
2. Interventions aimed at reducing depression should focus on developing and strengthening social connections, and mental health professionals should consider the unique experiences and circumstances of individuals when developing treatment plans.
3. Future research should aim to explore the mechanisms underlying the relationships between religiosity, social support, and depression, and examine the impact of religiosity and social support on other mental health outcomes.
4. Policymakers should prioritize funding for programs that enhance social support networks for individuals struggling with depression, and develop policies that promote social connections and community engagement.

5. Mental health professionals should assess social support networks as part of depression diagnosis and treatment planning, and consider religiosity as a potential secondary or indirect factor in addressing depression.
6. By adopting a comprehensive approach that addresses the complex relationships between religiosity, social support, and depression, we can work towards developing more effective strategies for reducing depression and promoting good mental health.

5.4 LIMITATION AND SUGGESTION FOR FURTHER STUDIES

- The use of self-report measures for religiosity, social support and depression may be subject to biases and limitations, so it is advisable for further research to incorporate objective measures and multiple assessment methods, as well as the use of mixed-methods approaches to gain deeper understanding.
- This study's measures of religiosity may not capture the full complexity of religious beliefs and practices, so therefore, further research should consider cultural or individual differences in religiosity and social support.
- The study's sample size may be limited, reducing the statistical power to detect significant relationships between variables. Thus, further researchers should replicate with larger and diverse samples.

- There should be considerations for control of additional variable, such as personality or coping styles, and also examine relationships with other mental health outcomes.
- The study's findings may not be generalizable to other contexts or populations; therefore, researchers should explore their relationship in different context or populations.
- Time constrain was also a limitation factor as the researcher simultaneously engage in this study with other academic work, while time devoted for the research work was consequently cut down on.

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